

Distribution of Single Particle Energy and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

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In this note, we argue that it is energy and not momentum which is distributed in a Maxwell-Boltzmann equilibrium situation. In the simplest case, one has two particle elastic scattering such that: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4)$. Taking \ln of the second equation and equating to the first, multiplied by a constant $-1/T$, yields: $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. Momentum does not enter into this derivation. One may later introduce momentum degeneracy linked with e through $\int dp$ (in 3D or $\int dp$ in 1D) when calculating $C \int dp \exp(-e/T) = 1$ and $C \int dp \exp(-e/T) e = e_{ave}$. Thus, momentum is used to describe the degeneracy of e , but it is not used to calculate the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor, we argue.

This argument has implications because one may consider n particles (moving in 1-dimension) with total energy E . One may ask (as in (1)): What is the probability to have one particle with energy e ? For this case, (1) writes: $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} p(i)p(i) = RR-ee$ where $E = RR/2m$ and $p(i)$ is the one-dimensional momentum of the i th particle. This defines an $n-1$ sphere which is taken to be proportional to the probability. The issue we have with the assumption is that it is an argument based on momentum, not energy distribution. In other words, it is a distribution based on components of a vector. The approach of (1) does apply to a distribution of vector components. For example, for the case $n=2$, it yields the probability distribution for a 2-vector (p_x, p_y) given in (3). We argue, however, that the Maxwell-Boltzmann equilibrium is associated with a distribution of e (single particle energy) and not momentum and so one should not use the $n-1$ sphere associated with $p(i)$ (momentum) components in this case.

Simple Maxwell-Boltzmann Argument Based Strictly on Energy

One way to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is to use reaction balance for 2-body elastic collisions. The key here is the elasticity, i.e. the conservation of energy. Momentum is conserved, but momentum is ignored in a reaction balance equation, i.e.

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and equating to a constant $-1/T$ multiplied by ((1a)) yields:

$$\ln(P(e)) = -e/T \quad \text{or} \quad P(e) = C \exp(-e/T) \quad ((2))$$

At this point, momentum has not appeared. It appears when one wishes to sum over e . Then one needs to introduce cells in momentum space, not in energy space. The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution ((2)), however, is obtained from considerations in energy (not momentum). Thus, for a 3-D case:

$$C \int dp \exp(-e/T) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad C \int dp \exp(-e/T) e = e_{ave} \quad ((3))$$

and for a 1-D case $4\pi p dp$ is replaced with dp .

Thus momentum and degeneracy of momentum are reserved for a final summation. A second example is geometric summation used to obtain the Planck distribution for a photon, i.e.

Sum over $i \exp(-e_i n/T)$ where $n=1,2,3..$ ((4))

One sees that nowhere does momentum appear in the sum, i.e. the momentum degeneracy is not involved when one tries to create an energy distribution, we argue. We thus suggest that a Maxwell-Boltzmann type energy distribution is based on energy, not momentum distribution. Momentum degeneracy is used for summation of states associated with a given energy e (single particle). Does this statement have practical consequences? We argue that it does and consider this question in the next section.

N-1 Dimensional Sphere and Probability

In (1), a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas of particles moving in 1-dimension has a energy equation which may be written in terms of $p(i)p(i)$ where $p(i)$ is the 1-dimensional momentum of the i th particle:

Sum over $i=1,n$ $p(i)p(i) = RR$ ((5))

This is the equation of an n -sphere. If one sets the energy of one particle to e , then:

Sum over $i=1,n-1$ $p(i)p(i) = RR-ee$ ((6))

This is an $n-1$ sphere and it is argued in (1) that the probability $P(e)$ is proportional to the surface area of the $n-1$ sphere. We suggest that this is an argument based on the distribution of momentum and not energy and so does not describe a Maxwell-Boltzmann situation which should be based on energy. In particular, the approach of (1) applies to the probability for a component of a vector. In the case of $n=2$, the result of (1):

$P(p) dp = C (1-p^2/RR)^{\text{power} \{ (n-3)/2 \}}$ ((7))

is exactly the result for the probability of p_x in the vector (p_x, p_y) with a fixed magnitude R as seen in (2).

An energy based argument, on the other hand, is given in (3). For two particles, if one has energy e , the other has energy $E-e$. One may choose e uniformly from $(0,E)$ and each value corresponds to only one value of the second particle, thus leading to a constant energy distribution. The argument of (3) is that an energy based situation leads to:

$P(e) = C (E-e)^{\text{power}(n-2)}$ ((8))

For large n , one sees that ((7)) has an exponent of $n/2$ while ((8)) has one of n . The $n/2$ argument follows by considering momentum as the variable distributed, while n considers energy as the distributed variable.

We consider a simple example with $n=3$, a total energy of 6 and energy increments of 1. Then:

$P(e=6)$ yields (0,0) for the remaining two particles.

$P(e=5)$ yields (1,0), (0,1)

$P(e=4)$ yields (2,0) (0,2) (1,1)

$P(e=3)$ yields (3,0) (0,3), (2,1) (1,2) ((9))

Using ((8)) one expects $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)$ power 1 so $P(e=6) \rightarrow 0$, $P(e=5) \rightarrow 1$ $P(e=4) \rightarrow 2$ $P(e=3) \rightarrow 3$. These are all off by 1.

If one considers ((7)) $(3-3)/2=0$, i.e. one has a constant probability, which does not match the problem. Here $P(p)dp = P(p=\sqrt{2me}) dp$, where dp is used in the "summation".

For $E=6$, $n=4$, one has: $e=6$ 1 state, $e=5$, 3 states, $e=4$, 6 states and $e=3$, 10 states.

$(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ predicts 0,1,4,9 while $(E-e)$ power $(n-3)/2$ predicts 0,1, 1.71, a number less than 1.8.

The approach of (1) is based on a probability proportional to the surface area of an $n-1$ sphere i.e. proportional to: $(E-e)$ power $(n-1)/2$. If one uses this probability, then for $n=3$, one has: $(E-e)$ which is the same as the $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ approach. For four particles: 0,1,3,4, about 5.4. Thus, this also does not describe the energy distribution.

The momentum based approach does not describe the pure energy distribution situation. It only applies to problems in which it is momentum and not energy which is distributed, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a simple energy balance approach to obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution depends on elastic collisions. In other words, it is energy which is distributed, not momentum. $P(e)=C\exp(-e/T)$ follows without any consideration of momentum. It is only when one sums over that one must bring in the degeneracy associated with momentum cells. If one takes this idea seriously, it means that even though a gas of n particles moving in 1-dimension is described by: $\sum_{i=1}^n p(i)p(i)=RR$ where $E=RR/2m$, i.e. an n -sphere, this sphere is associated with momentum distribution, not energy distribution. By considering an n -sphere, one considers an n -vector and the distribution of components of the vector. In particular, if the n th particle has energy e , the approach of (1) is to assign a probability proportional to the surface area of an $n-1$ sphere (proportional to $(RR-pp)$ power $(n-1)/2$ multiplied by $Rd\theta$ where $R\cos(\theta)R\cos(\theta) = RR-pp$ and $E=RR/2m$. This, however, is a distribution based on momentum, not energy, which seems to contradict the energy argument

used to find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for reaction balance of elastic 2-body collisions. Such an argument does not consider momentum at all when deriving $\exp(-e/T)$. Momentum degeneracy only appears when summing over e , i.e. one uses dp instead of de for 1-dimension or $4\pi p^2 dp$ for 3-dimensions.

References

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